

D 6.2 – Report on simulation studies for controller tuning and validation

HighScape - High efficiency, high power density, cost effective, scalable and modular power electronics and control solutions for electric vehicles

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Long Version
ABS	antilock braking system
AVLDE	AVL Deutschland GmbH

BEV	Battery electric vehicle
BFD	Brake Force Distribution
BLU	Bluways International B.V.B.A.
CA	Control allocation
ELA	Elaphe Propulsion Technologies Ltd.
EV	Electric vehicle
FL	Front left
FOC	field-oriented torque controller
FT	FIAT TOFAŞ
HVAC	high-voltage AC
IWM	in-wheel machine / in-wheel motor
MiL	model-in-the-loop
PE	Power Electronics
PHM	Prognostic Health Management
PID	proportional-integral-derivate
PnG	Pulse-and-Glide
POLITO	Politecnico di Torino
RR	Rear right
SOTIF	safety of the intended function
TE	Tracking error
TUIL	Technische Universität Ilmenau
USR	University of Surrey
WBG	Wide bandgap

Table of Contents

1	Publishable Executive Summary	4
1.1	Overview of project.....	4
1.2	Deliverable Objective and Results.....	4
2	Introduction	5
3	Simulation studies.....	6
3.1	Low-level control for traction inverter.....	6
3.2	Thermal Management.....	6
3.2.1	Interface Definition	6
3.2.2	Control Strategy Adaption and Software implementation.....	8
3.3	Vehicle Level control actions.....	9
3.3.1	Controller for intelligent brake force distribution	9
3.3.2	Controller for energy recovery	10
3.3.3	Controller for antilock brake system	11
3.3.4	Controller for Pulse-and-glide electric motor control	13
3.3.5	Controller for RL optimized longitudinal oscillation reduction	13
4	Conclusion.....	15
4.1	General Conclusion	15
4.2	Deviations, Impact and Recovery Actions.....	15
5	Bibliography	16

List of Figures

FIGURE 1: OVERVIEW OF SIMULATION FRAMEWORK WITH EXTERNAL COMPONENTS	6
FIGURE 2: SENSORS LAYOUT FOR TEST BED (UPPER) AND DEMONSTRATOR VEHICLE (LOWER) VALIDATION	7
FIGURE 3: COMPARISON OF THE VALVE1 CONTROL STRATEGIES.....	8
FIGURE 4: OVERVIEW IN AND OUTPUTS PROTECTED CONTROLLER MODEL	8
FIGURE 5: COMPARISON OF THE BRAKING DISTANCES ON HIGH (LEFT) AND LOW μ SURFACE (RIGHT) WITH VARYING MAXIMUM BRAKING INTENSITY	9
FIGURE 6: ENERGETIC COMPARISON BETWEEN THE EVC1000 VEHICLE DEMONSTRATOR AND A BASELINE AUDI E-TRON (SEE [4]).....	10
FIGURE 7: PEDAL CHANGE BEHAVIOUR FOR HEADING TOWARDS A RED TRAFFIC LIGHT	11
FIGURE 8: KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS FOR DEVELOPED ABS CONTROL FOR DIFFERENT ROAD ADHESION CONDITIONS (SEE [7]).....	12

List of Tables

TABLE 1: NUMERIC VALUES OF THE RESULTS OBTAINED FROM DRIVER-IN-THE-LOOP SIMULATION.....	11
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1 Publishable Executive Summary

1.1 Overview of project

Focused on BEV architectures with distributed multiple wheel drives, and, specifically, in-wheel powertrains, HighScape will explore the feasibility of a family of highly efficient power electronics components and systems, and including integrated traction inverters, onboard chargers, DC/DC converters, and electric drives for auxiliaries and actuators. The proposed solutions will be assessed on test rigs and on two differently sized BEV prototypes.

The project will result in:

- i. component integration with the incorporation of the WBG traction inverters within the in-wheel machines to achieve zero footprint of the electric powertrain on the sprung mass; the functional integration of the traction inverter with the on-board charger, and the incorporation of the latter and the DC/DC converters within the battery pack; and the implementation of multi-motor and fault-tolerant inverter solutions for the auxiliaries and chassis actuators;
- ii. novel solutions, including the implementation of reconfigurable winding topologies of the drive, as well as integrated and predictive thermal management at the vehicle level, with the adoption of phase changing materials within the power electronics components;
- iii. the achievement and demonstration of significantly higher levels of power density, specific power and energy efficiency for the resulting power electronics systems and related drives;
- iv. major cost reductions thanks to the dual use of parts, subsystem modularity, and model-based design to eliminate overengineering; and
- v. increased dependability and reliability of the power electronics systems, enabled by design and intelligent predictive health monitoring algorithms.

Through HighScape, the participants will establish new knowledge and industrial leadership in key digital technologies, and, therefore, directly contribute to Europe's Key Strategic Orientations as well as actively support the transformation towards zero tailpipe emission road mobility (2Zero).

1.2 Deliverable Objective and Results

Work package 6 is generally dealing with the development, realization, implementation and functional testing of relevant high- and low-level controls for an optimal performance on component, system and vehicle level as well. Task 6.2 targets to validate the control performance via advanced testing model-in-the-loop (MiL) testing with the simulation framework and surrogate model from Work Package 2.

2 Introduction

After deliverable D6.1 presented the control strategies and basic control laws, this report is about the testing and simulation-based validation of the desired functionality. The latter one is also relevant to evidence *safety of the intended function (SOTIF)*, even if it is not referring to the corresponding guideline ISO/PAS 21448.

Regarding the different sub-systems and levels of the controls (see deliverable D6.1, Figure 16-17), multiple tasks arise from the project to be reported in the document as follows:

- Testing of **PE low-level controllers** (incl. electric gear) with consideration of **EMI/EMC features**
- Testing of the **vehicle performance controllers** with regard to active safety, energy efficiency and ride comfort
- Consideration of **health management strategies** to enhance component and vehicle lifetime
- **Advanced and holistic thermal management** for optimal system performance and efficiency

The responsibilities, testing setups and achievements for the aforementioned bullet points are described in the next sections.

3 Simulation studies

3.1 Low-level control for traction inverter

The low-level control is basically a field-oriented torque controller (FOC), which - from power electronics point of view - is equivalent to a current controller. It assumes to receive the required set-points of the required current from the high-level controller logic and using the available sensors and actuators to control the inverter currents to the requested values. The control strategy then orients the stator current vector in a rotating reference frame of the machine as described by Strobl [1]. Based on Fernandez [2], this vector current control (also known as *dq current control*) is a widespread method for three-phase AC currents, which uses a rotating reference frame, synchronized with the grid voltage. The PMSM control algorithm implemented by BLU follows these well-known engineering approaches, as documented in the report D6.1 already. The tuning of the controller is based on longstanding expertise and knowledge, on the real component and will be further reported in the deliverable D6.3.

3.2 Thermal Management

3.2.1 Interface Definition

In the deliverable D5.1 the VTMS for the vehicle has been developed. The environment was built up as a simulation model which is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Overview of simulation framework with external components

The developed controller will be used on the test bed at Politecnico di Torino (POLITO) and in FIAT demonstrator vehicle. Since there were smaller updates to the original layout, the layout with sensor positions is shown in Figure 2. For the validation of the developed layout and the components several sensors are needed and therefore will be implemented into the test bed, but installation in the vehicle is more difficult. To implement all sensors will increase the costs and complexity of the system. Since the validation of the layout will be done on the test bed the numbers of implemented sensors in the vehicle can be reduced. It is common for only very few sensors to be implemented in production vehicles. The goal is to use the same controller for the testbed and the demonstration vehicle. Since not all vehicle sensor data and their availability were clear during the built up of the controller, the control strategy was

D 6.2 – Report on simulation studies for controller tuning and validation

implemented as if it had access to all inputs shown in the Figure 2. As the project progressed, discussions intensified regarding the absolute need of sensors for feasible integration on the one hand and the cost and effort estimation on the other. The result of the discussions led to the layout shown in Figure 2. The flow sensors were omitted in the cooling circuit and a total of ten temperature sensors are used in the cooling and refrigeration circuit, in the environment and the cabin. Pressure is measured at two positions in the refrigeration circuit. This is necessary to determine the sub-cooling after the condenser of the automatic cooling system. Additionally, the relative humidity in the cabin and the environment is measured.

Figure 2: Sensors layout for test bed (upper) and demonstrator vehicle (lower) validation

3.2.2 Control Strategy Adaption and Software implementation

The control system developed in the first loop requires various input signals, but there is only a reduced number of sensors available, so the control strategy and actuators had to be adjusted. The originally planned freely controllable 3/2-way valves were replaced by 2/2-way valves. This led to a change in the control strategy. With the 3/2-way valves, it was planned to use a proportional-integral-derivate (PID) controller to reach a target temperature for the position after the pump (T11). For valves with just two positions this strategy is not suitable since the valve will then open and close too fast. For that reason, a hysteresis-based control block was implemented in the control strategy as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Comparison of the valve1 control strategies

Figure 4: Overview in and outputs protected controller model

In the given example for valve1 the valve opens if the temperature goes above 64 °C and will close if the temperature drops below 60 °C. The hysteresis setpoints are chosen from knowledge of previous projects and need to be tested in the demonstration vehicle. The adjustments also had some changes on other setpoints of the control strategy. The previous plan was for example to open the valve at T11 = 63 °C and to activate the fan for temperatures T11 > 65 °C. With the hysteresis strategy those setpoints need to be adapted a bit. The same procedure must be applied to other valves where 3/2-way valves are replaced by two shutoff valves. There were several other changes to the strategy for other actuators. There is a restriction on the fan, which can only operate at two speed levels. The high-voltage AC (HVAC) box in the

demonstration vehicle is taken over from the series vehicle. External control of the actuators in this unit (such as recirculation flap, blower and air flap) is not possible. The control strategy for those actuators is already implemented in this blackbox component.

The algorithm for the thermal management is built up in Simulink® (see Figure 4) and needs to be implemented on the control unit of the FT vehicle. To protect the intellectual property of AVLDE, no further input is given in this document. The controller will take over the tasks of controlling the actuators in the vehicle. For this purpose, the input signals from the vehicle are used and output signals are sent to the actuators.

3.3 Vehicle Level control actions

3.3.1 Controller for intelligent brake force distribution

Brake force distribution (BFD) is a crucial part regarding vehicle active safety. Using too less braking force on the corners wastes potential and leads to longer braking distances. On the other hand, if too much braking force is applied, the wheels tend to lock and the braking distance increases too and may lead to instabilities when braking while cornering. Therefore, a well-balanced BFD needs to be found to provide vehicle safety, stability and comfort. Commonly, the front axle gains more braking force, since the vehicle body inertia leads to a shift of wheel load from the rear to the front axle, which increases the pressure in the tire patch and therefore the adhesion potential with the road. With regard to vehicles with rear-wheel drive (RWD), this approach is not very beneficial, especially when it comes to electric drivetrains. The ability of electric machines to recover energy during braking leads to an improved energy balance and should be maximized at all costs, but classical BFD do not support this approach. Therefore, new methods are necessary. Spichartz and Sourkounis [3] investigated different BFDs for front- and rear-wheel driven, electric vehicles targeting the improvement of energy recovery while maintaining vehicle safety. As already presented in deliverable D6.1, the new BFD allocates a specific amount to the rear-axle first, before the braking force on the front axle gets increased. This allows pure regenerative braking at low decelerations. To evidence active safety and vehicle stability, some straight-line braking tests on high and low adhesion coefficient road were conducted in simulation. The initial velocity was 70 km/h and the maximum braking ratio was limited to the shown thresholds (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Comparison of the braking distances on high (left) and low μ surface (right) with varying maximum braking intensity

The results prove, that the new BFD (marked as “adaptive” in Figure 5) guarantees a safe braking and the difference to the ideal BFD from the ECE regulation No. 13 is less than 3 % in all manoeuvres. Further, this brake force distribution was already implemented in the vehicle demonstrator of EVC1000 and tested on public road, showing no remarkable safety deficits.

3.3.2 Controller for energy recovery

One basic function of electric vehicles is the ability to recover kinetic energy. The relevance of this control was shown in [4], by showing the impact on the energy consumption with and without control. The basic controller was adapted from previous Horizon2020 project *Electric Vehicle Components for 1000 km daily trips* (EVC1000) but is now combined with the new BFD to enhance the recovery rate. Since the simulation framework do neither use a validated model of the electric machines nor of the traction battery of the target vehicle, the controller efficacy was tested in the EVC1000 vehicle demonstrator, since it uses similar components. The outcomes are depicted in Figure 6 and were also published in [4]. From the plots, it can be seen that the new BFD increased the amount of pure regenerative braking up to series level (black dashed line). This is quite impressive, since the series AUDI e-tron features electric all-wheel drive and can regenerate at up to 220 kW due to official information from AUDI. Thanks to the very effective working and torque-dense in-wheel machines, the missing electric drive at the front axle of the EVC1000 demonstrator was successfully compensated. In the right plot, the amount of recovered energy raised significantly, which indicates a better overall energy balance, proving efficacy of the implemented control.

Figure 6: Energetic comparison between the EVC1000 vehicle demonstrator and a baseline AUDI e-tron (see [4])

Note: The next section deals with an innovative control design, that was no original part of the HighScope project. However, the achievements are promising and might be a starting point for future research.

A possible enhancement of the controller was further investigated in some internal research, which is not directly linked to HighScope, but shows potential for future research activities. The previous section was about regenerative braking, that is triggered by pressing down the brake pedal. But in some scenarios, this approach wastes potential as shown in Figure 7. When heading to a switching traffic light, most drivers release the drive pedal first before pressing the brake pedal down. Moreover, if the brake pedal is applied

quite late, the high deceleration demand prevents activation of regenerative braking. If there is a control, which activates the regenerative torque as soon as the drive pedal position falls under a specific threshold, energy can be recovered until application of the brake pedal.

Figure 7: Pedal change behaviour for heading towards a red traffic light

Since this enables the driver to control the vehicle speed with just the drive pedal, literature refers to this control as *one-pedal driving*. A possible realization and testing of the controller was published in [5]. A more precise description of the controller can be found there and the preliminary results in Table 1. The results are derived from a subject study, that was conducted at TUIL facilities with volunteers on a static driving simulator. All participants were instructed to drive as usual on a road segment of 13 kilometers length with equal parts of driving in the city, on rural roads and highway sections. In total, every participant had to pass the cycle four times with different configurations of the control, see Table 1. A precise description of the control setup is given in [5].

Table 1: Numeric values of the results obtained from driver-in-the-loop simulation

	$E_{el,cum}$ [kWh/100 km]	RI [%]	N_{BPA} [-]
Reference	24.90 ± 1.91	24.43 ± 1.84	53.53 ± 12.36
OPD-1	22.89 ± 1.73	37.28 ± 2.87	5.93 ± 2.94
OPD-2	22.35 ± 1.25	40.74 ± 1.86	20.80 ± 4.34
OPD-2.1	22.36 ± 1.12	40.46 ± 3.07	9.20 ± 4.13

3.3.3 Controller for antilock brake system

The antilock braking system (ABS) is a mandatory safety feature for releasing new vehicles. It aims to reduce the braking distance by maintaining a desirable wheel slip and prevent the wheels from locking to guarantee a satisfactory force transmission between tires and underground. In HighScope, the advantages of an electromechanical brake-by-wire system on ABS performance shall be investigated, promising better results due to the higher actuation dynamics of electromechanics compared to (electro)hydraulics. Moreover, the impact of continuous wheel slip tracking is compared to the classical rule-based control approach. The continuous control approaches were already reported in deliverable D6.1 and in Heydrich

D 6.2 – Report on simulation studies for controller tuning and validation

et al. [6] too. Due to the shift of work on the brake-by-wire system, the tests were carried out on the hybrid system from EVC1000 to accelerate the project. The results are discussed below. At this point, it should be mentioned that the improvements shown there are expected to be even higher by using the electro-mechanical front calipers. To evidence this, further experiments are necessary as soon as the physical prototype is available.

In total, five different conditions were investigated within the experiments as shown in Figure 8 to cover most of daily use cases. White bars indicate the maximum of all considered simulations, while the colored ones indicate the minimum, respectively. Every condition was tested at five different initial speeds for the continuous proportional-integral (PI) and integral sliding mode (ISM) as well as the classical rule-based (RB) approach. Every simulation was repeated at least five times, giving a total of 375 simulation data sets. For the studies, a vehicle model from EVC1000 project was used in simulation environment CarMaker. Through majority of all simulations, the continuous controls showed superior performance against the RB one. The results on left column are less interesting, since high adhesion road ensures a safe braking.

Figure 8: Key performance indicators for developed ABS control for different road adhesion conditions (see [7])

More interesting are the braking events under severe like braking on low adhesion or a spontaneous decrease of adhesion (long. split μ). Here, the differences in performance are very obvious. The braking distance (s_{br}) in the low μ manoeuvres was up to 13.8 % (approximately 26 m) lower than the rule-based ABS. Quite similar behaviour can be found for the manoeuvres with a spontaneous adhesion change during braking, so called “ μ jump manoeuvres”, where the braking distance was decreased by 10-13 %. Further the tracking error (TE) of optimal wheel slip became lower by up to 60 %, which is a remarkable indicator for the controller’s efficacy. Especially, the rear axle with electromechanical calipers (indicated by the rear right (RR) corner in Figure 8) showed lower peak values due to the high(er) actuation dynamics. The electrohydraulic calipers on the front (indicated by the front left (FL) corner in Figure 8) acted better with the new controller tuning, but the lower dynamics lead to higher tracking errors as well.

The middle column indicates braking with different adhesion coefficients on both sides of the vehicle to investigate stability. In the experiments, the performance improvement towards active safety was higher at low speeds, but in general the continuous approaches performed better in all cases. Regarding the lateral stability, all three approaches were able to keep the vehicle on track with a maximum yaw rate of less than 3 deg/s. This value is low enough to be controlled by any kind of driver, neglecting his driving skill level, so no further comments are made here.

In the rightmost column, the manoeuvre contains a very inhomogeneous surface with patches of different adhesion coefficients. This simulates bad weather conditions with small water films or even puddles on the road. The results are similar to the longitudinal split scenario, but with one exception: the differences between rule-based and continuous approaches are smaller than before. However, all approaches kept the vehicle stable on track, which was the main target of the ABS.

3.3.4 Controller for Pulse-and-glide electric motor control

This work explores the mathematical formulation and theoretical analysis of the pulse-and-glide (PnG) driving strategy for electric vehicles (EVs) and its integration with control allocation (CA) to optimize energy efficiency. While PnG techniques have traditionally been studied in the context of internal combustion engines and hybrid vehicles, their application to EVs has only recently gained attention. The implementation of PnG in EVs is still evolving, presenting an opportunity to refine motor power loss management during the glide phase. This advancement could further enhance the effectiveness of this emerging eco-driving strategy. The mathematical formulation of the control technique and literature review of the proposed controller were submitted in the deliverable D6.1 (annex).

This work is currently in progress for a publication. The whole development and results will be available in an open-access journal in the near future. For now, the results are included in the confidential annex of this document.

3.3.5 Controller for RL optimized longitudinal oscillation reduction

This study aims to develop an AI-driven controller to improve vehicle comfort by applying torque corrections to the in-wheel motors (IWMs). The controller is designed to minimize longitudinal oscillations of the sprung mass and reduce the oscillation of the relative speed between the sprung and unsprung masses on both axles, ultimately enhancing driver comfort. The controller seeks to achieve performance levels comparable to or surpassing those of model-based nonlinear approaches. It operates by taking

feedback inputs from the plant model and outputting torque corrections – either positive or negative – based on the driver’s requested torque, which is assumed to remain constant during the test.

The AI-based controller demonstrated high performance, comparable to a state-of-the-art model-based version, while significantly reducing oscillations compared to passive systems. It proved to be robust, maintaining its effectiveness across various road conditions and vehicle parameter variations. The results highlight that the AI-based controller is a scalable and computationally efficient solution for improving vehicle dynamics.

This work is currently in progress for a publication. The whole development and results will be available in an open-access journal in the near future. While the literature review, controller development, and training are detailed in D6.1 (annex), the results are included in the confidential annex of this document.

4 Conclusion

4.1 General Conclusion

This deliverable reported the recent findings for evaluation of the developed vehicle and component controls from multi-stage X-in-the-loop testing methods. Special interest lies on the high-level and vehicle performance controllers, since the take care of optimal control allocation among the different actuators and systems.

Especially in terms of vehicle dynamics and energy efficiency control, some interesting results were achieved e.g. with the advance brake torque blending and the use case of a possible enhancement by one-pedal driving, which improved dynamics, driver comfort and energy efficiency against the normal vehicle controller with regenerative braking control solely. This was evidenced by driver-in-the-loop experiments. Further, a pulse-and-glide control distributes the driving torque among the IWMs to propel the vehicle at minimal energy consumption level by reducing periods of high-torque demand. At last, a new ABS control is introduced and tested via hardware-in-the-loop simulation. Since development of the electromechanical brake-by-wire system did not progress far enough to have a running prototype already and since there was no surrogate model available at the moment of the reporting, simulations were performed on a hybrid brake-by-wire system from previous project EVC1000 (<https://evc1000.eu>), which features electromechanical calipers on the rear axle already. From the result – especially on the wheel slip tracking performance (see Figure 8) – it is assumed and partially shown already, that a full electromechanical brake system will perform way better. This hypothesis needs to be confirmed by using the real hardware during the tests in task 6.4.

4.2 Deviations, Impact and Recovery Actions

There was a slight delay of four weeks in submitting the report due to vacation and business trips in that time. The further work in the project in general and the WP in particular are not affected in any negative way by this.

5 Bibliography

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